

FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF THE CSI: CRISM SPECTRAL INTERROGATOR. C. E. Viviano, Johns Hopkins University Applied Physics Laboratory <Christina.Viviano@jhuapl.edu>.

Motivation: Evidence for widespread exposures of aqueous alteration in ancient Mars terrain (e.g., [1-3]) provides the latest drive in the search for zones of past habitable environments, and helps guide the selection of future sites for *insitu* investigation by rovers and eventually humans to Mars. Though tens of thousands of Compact Reconnaissance Imaging Spectrometer for Mars (CRISM) mapping and targeted resolution data products exist, a standardized way to catalog the detection of compositionally-unique outcrops with specific spectral signatures has yet to be established. The difficulty of cataloging the distribution and composition of these alteration phases can be attributed to the sheer volume of the available dataset to analyze, and the time-consuming nature of the traditional practices for identification of distinct mineralogic phases using CRISM hyperspectral data.

A total of 31 spectrally-unique phases have been identified using CRISM (over 20 of these are aqueous alteration products) and have been assembled into a type spectra library, the Minerals Identified through CRISM Analysis (MICA) Library [4]. The MICA library provides a basis for future analysis of CRISM data and summarizes the current state of knowledge in surface spectral variability. These 31 unique spectral signatures, when mapped across the surface of Mars in the full detail provided with the entire CRISM dataset, record an unprecedented level of detail about past aqueous environments on Mars.

The traditional CRISM analysis workflow is particularly time-consuming for a myriad of reasons and information a region of interest (ROI) where a spectrum is extracted is often not provided in published work [5]. To recreate spectra retrieved from a traditional CRISM analysis workflow, the following must be documented: image ID, location of numerator and denominator spectra (row and column position within the unprojected image), and dimensions of the ROIs used for each. This is only the case for standard (rectangular) ROIs and no additional undocumented processing to the spectra. This detailed documentation effort is oppressively burdensome for

regional studies and provides only the minimal information that is extractable from the dataset. ROI information documentation is often not provided in published work; typically, an arrow denotes the general location where numerator spectra were retrieved. This is detrimental to reproducibility and building upon previous efforts.

Here, we present an update on our development of a tool for efficiently and accurately accomplishing CRISM analysis, that we plan to make available to the greater Mars science community.

CSI Prototype: A prototype of the CRISM Spectral Interrogator (CSI, Fig. 1) is currently being further developed and has been used by several members of the APL CRISM team and their interns and student collaborators over the last ~6 years. The prototype CSI is a custom user interface that leverages widgets (graphical controls) provided by the IDL/ENVI platform. Developed in support of research projects being conducted by a handful of CRISM team members, the prototype CSI has been used in several regional-scale studies, where such detailed analysis of hundreds of images would otherwise not have been possible. These studies [5,6,7] used this tool to identify and publish the location of thousands of outcrops with classified spectral compositions using high-resolution

Figure 1. Prototype CSI display and plot windows. Standard and custom RGB composites of summary products in upper windows, and plots with numerator (red ROI, red spectrum), denominator (green ROI, green spectrum), and ratioed spectra (black spectrum) compared to lab spectra (dark green).

targeted and mapping-mode data. The ability to report this level of detail in CRISM analysis is unprecedented for investigations where automated detection routines are not used. With the CSI tool, images can be probed for their unratioed and ratioed spectra, displayed with single left/right mouse clicking and automatic column alignment, ancillary metadata is automatically acquired and stored, and each location may be characterized and classified as one or more specific endmembers defined in [4]. We anticipate that the use of this tool will allow for improved global mapping and sharing between members of the Mars community. Further, the CSI will lower the learning barrier for those familiar with spectroscopy but who may not have experience using CRISM data.

The current prototype-CSI output data files (text files) can be read into JMARS and mapped using the custom shape layer tool that exists within JMARS (see Fig. 2). This functionality combined with the other analytical and browsing tools within JMARS and ArcGIS has been useful for previous investigations [5,6,7]. In figure 2, we display the point locations identified in the prototype-CSI tool as different colors to indicate the different identified mineralogies. Both JMARS and ArcGIS will be able to access all ancillary information saved in the standard file and associate it to each analysis. These data are draped over a 3-d rendering of the surface to provide contextual information about their distribution across the surface (Fig. 2).

Upcoming Plans: We are currently working on making the CSI tool compatible with a myriad of CRISM data products (MTRDRs, TERs, TRR3) and types (FRT, HRL, MSP, etc.). In order for the functionality of this tool to be ready to deliver to the greater planetary remote sensing community, there are several tasks left to complete. These include updating and supporting user-informed spectral ratioing, further development of a standard output data file format for external Geographic Information System (GIS) packages (e.g., JMARS, ArcGIS), software validation, and public release of the IDL source code (as an add-on to the CAT), and an IDL license-free VM bundle.

Acknowledgements: This work is funded by PDART Grant #80NSSC21K0884.

References: [1] Carter, et al. (2013), *JGR*, 118(4), 831–858. [2] Ehlmann, and. Edwards (2014), *Annu. Rev. Earth Planet. Sci.*, 42. [3] Pan and Ehlmann (2014), *GRL*, 41(6), 1890–1898. [4] Viviano-Beck et al. (2014), *JGR*, 119(6), 1403-1431. [5] Viviano-Beck et al. (2017), *Icarus*, 284, 43–58. [6] Viviano et al. (2019), *Icarus*, 328, 274-286. [7] Phillips et al. (2022), *Geology*, 50(10), 1182-1186.

Figure 2. Mapping-view integration of prototype CSI data into JMARS. The shapefiles resulting from the prototype CSI standard file uses color schemes for mineral identification output from the CSI and automatically read into a JMARS custom .csv shapefile.